

Transformation of the Ordinary Factory into a Smart Factory: Design and Conception

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ABSTRACT

The increasing global competition between companies from different regions with different economic conditions leads them to increase the variety of their products to meet the needs of their customers, and this, by resorting to mass customization. In addition, they must increase the flexibility of their production systems in terms of resource capacity, quantities produced, and the use of technologies to better respond to a volatile and hyper-competitive market. The arrival of the fourth industrial revolution, known as Industry 4.0 (I4.0), promises improvements in productivity, flexibility, and integration of production systems. To swiftly move to this fourth industrial revolution and raise this challenge, companies must digitize their processes by implementing various technological levers, which utilize decentralized decisions through system connectivity and real-time communication. Inevitably, several factories must adopt these new technologies and transform themselves towards total digitization of these production processes. The organizations of these factories must also meet the requirements of this digital transformation for better integration into the global supply chain for shock absorbers and similar products.

As a contribution, we chose an industrial food-processing factory to transform it into an intelligent factory using the Factory IO software. The transformation relies on the use of the interconnection of some new technologies related to digital, such as the wireless sensors that can provide machines the ability to see, detect and communicate more intelligently.

KEYWORDS

Industry 4.0; Digital Transformation; Smart Factory; Digital Technologies, Manufacturing Systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

The industry makes extensive use of automation. An automatic system always seeks to perform a certain number of operations without human intervention. In some cases, the goal is to replace humans for economic reasons, to save them from painful tasks, or to obtain a better-quality product.

Advances in robots, mobile communications, and information technology have led to a global shift in the usage of digital technologies in industries. A new industrial revolution has been sparked by the growth of the digital economy and its effects on the world economy. Because of its significance to the business, innovative ideas and trends to improve how well organizations operate have been developed; this is the industry 4.0 project.

The Internet of Things, Intelligent Sensors, and Artificial Intelligence are among the main technological innovations that mark the future trends of the digital economy and the global economy of tomorrow.

The Fourth Industrial Revolution relies on digitalization. The smart grids establishment will enable the creation of intelligent factories, industries, and processes that will result in improved, flexibility, productivity, and better use of material and human resources.

In this article, we primarily want to give a brief overview of the intelligent factory, its many cutting-edge technologies, and some key implementation guidelines. In this context, we will show through an example how to transform an ordinary factory into a smart one using the Factory IO software.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 sheds light on this fourth industrial revolution by presenting its different concepts, various technologies, and expected benefits. Section 3 focuses on an example of an ordinary factory producing juice via a brief description of the manufacturing process.

Section 4 presents the design, tools, and technologies used to transform the factory described in the previous section into a smart factory. Finally, Section 5 concludes this paper with future work proposals.

2. INDUSTRY 4.0 AND THE ADVENT OF THE SMART FACTORY

Global industrial usage of digital technologies is rising as a result of advancements in robotics, mobile communications, and information technology. "Industry 4.0" is the name given to this transition, which comes after the revolutions brought about by the steam engine, assembly line, and automation (the development of electronics).

This section is devoted to introducing this new industrial revolution (industry 4.0), the innovative technologies involved in its appearance, their expected benefits, and their issues to take into account.

2.1 General Format, Page Layout and Margins

The "Industry 4.0" is an industrial project introduced in 2010 in Hanover at the industrial technology fair ("Cebit"). It was officially presented and supported by Chancellor Angela Merkel at the 2012 show. It is a key project of the high technology strategy of the German government in which industrial/ professional federations are strongly mobilized (Pinheiro et al., 2022).

The Industry 4.0 project aims to develop new production organizations throughout the value chain. The "Industry 4.0" is announced as the 4th Industrial Revolution (see Figure.1). The 1st industrial revolution was triggered in the 1780s by the first mechanized production plant creation. Thanks to the invention of the steam engine. The 2nd industrial revolution began in 1850, with electricity invention and mass production. In the 1970s, the 3rd industrial revolution launched, the automated production era with the development of electronics and the beginnings of automation and industrial IT. Nowadays, the 4th industrial revolution begins, with the Internet of connected objects and the cloud, to increase the flexibility of production and manufacturing using intelligent systems, such as simulation systems and smart sensors, etc. (Balog et al., 2021).

Figure 1. Evolution of industries

2.2 Major technologies used in Factory 4.0

In this sub-section, we cite the major technologies, which today represent a wide range of software and equipment that, when connected, can transform the manufacturing company into a smart one.

The Scopus database was chosen to extract major 4.0 technologies from the literature due to its extensive coverage of documents across various databases. Scopus offers comprehensive coverage, including publications and citations in the scientific and technological disciplines, allowing researchers to do backward and forward searches.

The search was conducted on December 10, 2024, using the following string: TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Digital transformation") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("industry 4.0") AND TITLE-ABSKEY ("technologies"). By utilizing the TITLE-ABSKEY operator, a Boolean search was performed, applying the specified query to titles, abstracts, and keywords. This search method successfully identified 389 articles that met the defined criteria. The results encompass journal articles and conference papers

- **Artificial Intelligence**

Artificial intelligence (AI) in Industry 4.0 is a disruptive force that incorporates cutting-edge technologies into industrial processes, increasing efficiency, productivity, and sustainability. This integration improves communication between physical and virtual systems, allowing for more intelligent operations across multiple sectors. AI optimizes industrial processes through predictive maintenance, customized production, and advanced data analytics, resulting in lower operational risks and improved performance metrics (Rai et al., 2024).

- **Internet of Things**

The Internet of Things (IoT) is the principal brick of industry 4.0. The sensor, associated with each object, measures the values for which it has been programmed and sends them, at regular intervals, to a database where they are analysed.

The IoT aspect of the fourth industrial revolution is using these connected objects in manufacturing processes. Thus, smart sensors and intelligent tools will be available in the factory. These technologies will help us to collect more data on the manufacturing process to verify compliance and optimize production in real-time.

However, the two primary challenges that are now impeding the massive issue of several billion shipments are the price and accessibility of IP addresses (Rejeb et al., 2022).

- **Big Data**

Data is produced by a variety of sources in the context of Industry 4.0, including people, infrastructure, sensors, and equipment. Because of the Internet of Things, for instance, a vast amount of data is now readily accessible (Aksa et al., 2021). With technologies like RFID (Radio Frequency Identification), collecting data has become simpler (Tribe et al., 2022). RFID and IoT technologies have made it possible to follow the products from their creations until the end of their lives. Therefore, the big data component can present chances for a new kind of maintenance, such predictive and preventative maintenance, and enable quality monitoring of the product throughout its life cycle (Qazi et al., 2022).

- **Digital twin**

A digital twin (DT) in Industry 4.0 is a virtual version of physical assets, processes, or systems that uses real-time data and advanced analytics to improve operational efficiency and innovation. This technology is critical for optimizing industrial processes, enabling predictive maintenance, and facilitating real-time monitoring, resulting in significant productivity gains and cost savings.

Digital twins are virtual duplicates of real systems that can be used to collect data and predict performance (Sethi et al., 2024). Digital twins optimize manufacturing operations using simulation-based methodologies, allowing for virtual commissioning and error detection (Florescu, 2024).

- **Cloud Computing**

New IT services like cloud computing and new infrastructure have been made possible by technological advancements. The industrial cloud is cloud computing implemented in the manufacturing sector; it is regarded as an advancement in current production practices (Berisha et al., 2022). It's a crucial component of industry 4.0, which improves control and connection amongst the many industrial processes (Pillen et al., 2023).

- **Cyber Security**

Robust and self-sufficient microcomputers, also known as embedded systems, are increasingly linked wirelessly to the Internet and to one another. Cyber-physical systems (CPS) are the result of the confluence of the virtual and physical worlds (cyberspace). With the release of the new IPv6 Internet protocol in 2012, there are now sufficient addresses available to enable intelligent items to be directly networked. Cyber-physical systems in the manufacturing sector comprise intelligent machinery, storage systems, and production facilities that have the ability to autonomously exchange information by initiating activities and managing their own operations. In certain instances, we even refer to "Cyber-Physical Human Systems (CPHS)," which combines sensors that enable physical environment monitoring with the human element as a source of information (Humayun et al., 2019).

- **Cobotic**

A robot called a Cobot (COLlaborative roBOT) is designed to manipulate items in tandem with a human operator. Generally speaking, it can be an automated system that works with cobotic connections or duties.

It is not necessary for cobots with several sensors and software to be isolated from human workers (see Figure. 3). Cobots in the smart factory will support the human operator (Faccio et al., 2022).

Figure 3. Collaborative robots (Khalid et al., 2016).

- **Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS)**

Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) are critical to the growth of Industry 4.0, as they enable the integration of digital and physical processes to improve industrial efficiency and responsiveness. CPS facilitates real-time data transmission and decision-making, which is critical in modern production contexts. The following sections discuss the essential components of CPS in Industry 4.0. CPS considerably improves operational efficiency by automating procedures and allowing for real-time monitoring (Serôdio et al., 2024). CPS-enhanced data analytics improves quality control while lowering defects and waste (Serôdio et al., 2024).

- **Additive manufacturing (AM)**

Additive manufacturing (AM) is critical to the development of Industry 4.0, which is defined by the integration of modern technologies and smart manufacturing systems. This collaboration improves operational efficiency, customisation, and sustainability in manufacturing processes. The following sections explain AM's significant contributions to Industry 4.0. AM enables real-time simulation and optimisation, therefore improving product lifecycle management (Jafar et al., 2024). These technologies enable networked smart factories, resulting in decentralised production and greater flexibility (Duvoisin et al., 2018).

2.3 How does a smart factory work?

A smart factory works according to six keys principles (Qu et al., 2019):

- The factory virtualization is applied to be able to simulate and follow 3D products, processes, and the production environment.
- The systems are interoperable: they can communicate and interact with each other.
- Decisions are decentralized: cyber-physical systems can make decisions independently.
- Analysis and decision-making are carried out in real-time, thanks to permanent and instant communication.
- It is service-oriented: it offers an ameliorated maintenance and other new services.
- It is modular: it adapts quickly to changing demands.

2.4 What are the expected benefits?

Through the development of product customisation and the reduction of time to market, Industry 4.0 seeks to make the product more appealing and inexpensive for the consumer while simultaneously improving the quality and services provided. In summary, with Industry 4.0, we are moving from mass production to large-scale and personalized production and the explosion of services (Müller et al., 2019).

Therefore, the primary beneficiary is the customer. The installation of intelligent modular production lines makes it possible to customize the product without additional costs or delays. The product quality is improved by immediate correcting and eliminating defects arising during manufacture and by increasing automatic controls.

For example, integrating an RFID chip into all components improves traceability and configuration control throughout the lifecycle (Zhou et al., 2009). The configuration analysis of the product, and its operating data (operations, environmental and production data) in real-time makes it possible to trigger a preventive maintenance intervention independently. The company also benefits from this industrial revolution through better communication and coordination between business lines. The logistics system can anticipate, for example, a request for parts from sensors measuring the stock level and the production progress. Real-time data management accelerates decision-making for operators and machines, which trigger actions on their own based on their information.

Improvements in working circumstances have a favorable effect on employees. Human has already been largely liberated from tedious and agonizing jobs by robotization (Yi et al., 2021).

Lastly, a sizable investment and anticipated profits have a major financial influence on the business. For instance, Airbus intends to cut its production costs by half.

2.5 Industry 4.0: Why is it among the priorities of leaders??

The world is changing faster than ever. Faced with the frenetic pace of the adoption of digital technology, organizations are looking to transform quickly. Operations can be disrupted by new goods and services, business strategies, and technology. In this situation, implementing Industry 4.0 concepts becomes essential. Tomorrow's leaders must be ready to adopt a new organizational structure. In this new economic landscape, Industry 4.0 will change companies in a number of ways: Business plan. Solutions for Industry 4.0 will transform how companies run. They will have an impact on the company's line of goods and services. Today, the new intelligent products and services are needed, However, new business models will soon become essential. Young businesses with innovative value models will also start to appear on the scene. In these circumstances, leaders will need to fully engage in the implementation of Industry 4.0. Companies must comprehend how the digital revolution will affect every aspect of their organization (Zheng et al., 2018).

The challenges of factory 4.0 are of several levels. The one usually put forward is technological: is the company capable of installing innovative technologies such as additive manufacturing (3D printing), augmented reality, robotics, etc.? The installation of these technologies and their connection with the existing tools introduce two other challenges: the interoperability between devices of different generations and cyber security (Yi et al., 2021).

In addition to technological issues, industry 4.0 is a cultural challenge and a human resources issue.

3. EXAMPLE OF AN ORDINARY FACTORY

In this section, we give a concise presentation of the general manufacturing process in the juice factory.

3.1 Description of produced products

Manufacturing is the result of the transformation of the raw materials into a product manufactured by an industrial process.

A manufactured product is the good or object resulting from human activity from raw materials, intending to fulfil a material, indirectly vital, helpful, or pleasant need for humans, a group, a society, an individual, etc.

A manufactured product can be a semi-finished product or a finished product.

The product made, in this factory, is a juice consisting mainly of syrup prepared in the factory and packed by a flexible paper also made in the same factory.

Finished products are classified into three types depending on the taste of syrup (wood fruit, strawberry, cocktail).

The company provides essential elements for producing juice: the raw materials for flexible paper manufacture, and ingredients for syrup preparation.

➤ ***The ingredients for the preparation of the syrup***

The ingredients that go into the preparation of the syrup are:

- **Water:** It is the main component of juice drinks. The water must be safe to drink in all respects, physical, chemical, microbiological, and toxicological. In the juice manufacturing plant, the water used is from the borehole. In this case, it is necessary to carry out several filtrations to eliminate particles of mineral and organic matter by the treatment units of the plant.
- **Sugar:** is an element that goes into the preparation of the syrup, the sugar used is sucrose.
- **Aromas:** are essential ingredients in the production of the refreshing drink in general. Their role is to offer a choice of tastes for the consumer. There are two kinds of flavors: natural flavors and artificial flavors for different tastes (wood fruit, cocktail, strawberry.)
- **Dyes:** food colors are essential in the preparation of syrup. First and foremost, they make the product aesthetically appealing to the consumer. Second, colorants correct natural color fluctuations of the beverage or color changes during production and storage processes. Finally, they help to preserve the identity or the character of some types of juice.

➤ ***Raw materials for making flexible paper***

- **Thermal paper:** is a base paper impregnated with several layers of chemical components, giving it heat-sensitive properties (see Figure.4). The factory uses this type of paper to make special flexible paper for packaging.

Figure 4. Thermal paper.

Aluminum: Aluminium has always been a widely used material for food packaging. Its essential role is to keep the product at an ideal temperature.

- **Thermoplastic materials (or thermoplastics):** They are linear macromolecular compounds. They are prepared by polymerization, copolymerization, or polycondensation (see Figure.5).

Thermoplastics have several common properties that derive from their structure and the forces that hold them together. This thermoplastic material is an essential element for food packaging.

Figure 5. Thermoplastic Materials.

3.1 Brief description of the manufacturing process

The factory has two workshops: the flexible paper manufacturing workshop and the syrup preparation and product manufacturing workshop.

➤ *The flexible paper manufacturing workshop*

In the flexible paper manufacturing workshop, the production process begins with the receipt of the raw material (virgin paper, aluminium, thermoplastic material). And it ends with a semi-finished product (a reel). Thus, the workshop is composed of the following five workstations:

- **Printing machine:** the printing machine is used in the first stage of the production cycle; on this machine is installed a roll of blank paper for printing. In this step, we use a printing technique called flexography which is often used in the world of packaging and, in particular, in the field of labels (see Figure.6). In this manufacturing workshop, the machine is intended to print three different models to have the three types of products mentioned above.

Figure 6. The printing machine.

Drilling machine: after the printing phase comes the paper piercing. This latter uses a drilling machine that aims to trace the printed coil dimensioning and mark the places of the straws (see Figure.7). This phase needs two operators to pilot, control, and ensure the proper functioning of this machine.

Figure 8. The drilling machine.

- **Production line:** In order to have a flexible paper intended for packaging, the pierced reel will be transferred to the production line; the result will be a semi-finished product. This phase needs three operators to ensure the production and the proper functioning of all the manufacturing stations of the line.

The production line is composed of three stations:

- In the first station, the paper will be covered by the thermoplastic material to have the inner layer of flexible paper.
- In the second station, the interior facade will be covered with aluminum and thermoplastic material.
- In the third station, which is the finishing phase, the paper will be finished by putting a layer of thermoplastic material on the outer side of this paper.

- **Cutting machine:** This cutting phase uses a cutting machine to have a finished product (see Figure.8). Just install the reel (semi-finished product) on the cutting machine to cut it into six small reels in order to have the finished product. This machine is controlled by an operator.

Figure 8. The cutting machine.

Figure.9 illustrates a diagram summarizing the manufacturing process of wrapping paper.

Figure 9. Wrapping paper production scheme.

➤ *The syrup preparation workshop*

● **Syrup production**

To properly start the production of the syrup, it is necessary, first of all, to make a water treatment. In this step, we use several filtrations to eliminate the particles of mineral, organic and microscopic matter.

After the treatment stage, we melt the sugar with the treated water and food preservatives to have a concentrated syrup.

In the final step, the concentrated syrup will be transferred using a pump to four tanks. Each tank has a total capacity of 1000 L. Also, each tank contains a food coloring and aroma type (strawberry, wood fruit, etc.).

● The filling machine

The production line consists of a conveyor and a filling machine. The conveyor is equipped with a guidance system to transport the empty juice boxes to the filling machine. Through the box presence detection sensor, the filling machine can fill a certain number of these boxes with the juice prepared previously at an optimal production speed.

At the end of this operation, we will have a finished product.

● The shrink wrapping machine

The shrink-wrapping machine is an industrial overwrapping machine intended for wrapping products (see Figure.10). At the end of the production line, the shrink wrapping machine ensures the grouping of products and their filming in the form of packs.

Figure 10. Example of an automatic shrink-wrapping machine with a shrink oven for grouping boxes or soft packages [19]

At the dawn of Industry 4.0, with all the possibilities of digital and connected objects, is it possible to imagine an intelligent factory that strengthens the company's competitiveness and aims to optimize the manufacturing process? The following section will answer this question.

4. TRANSFORMATION OF THE ORDINARY FACTORY INTO A SMART ONE

This section focuses on the design and simulation of an intelligent virtual juice factory (see Figure.11), which uses innovative technologies, using the Factory IO simulator; software for designing and simulating complete industrial systems.

4.1 Design, tools and technologies used

Figure 11. Virtual factory of juice manufacturing.

The virtual factory has three places reserved for three production lines to make the three types of products: strawberry, wood fruit, and cocktail (see Figure.12). Also, the virtual factory has three warehouses. Each warehouse stocks one of the three types of products mentioned above.

Figure 12. Production line.

A conveyor circuit is installed to transfer finished products to warehouses.

The finished product warehouse is a space dedicated to stocking the goods that come from production lines and are ready to be sold and shipped (see Figure.13). In the virtual factory, each production line has its warehouse.

Figure 13. Virtual factory warehouses.

The factory also contains three tanks. Each tank reserves a liquid representing the syrup of one of the three product types (see Figure.14).

The flow of liquid entering and exiting each liquid tank is managed by a capacitive level sensor, two regulatory valves. Pneumatic actuators, which may be positioned with signals between 0 and 10 V, are responsible for controlling regulatory valves. Keep in mind that liquid level detection is another use for capacitive sensors.

Each tank is characterized by:

- Height: 3 meters
- Diameter: 2 meters
- Drain pipe radius: 0.125 m
- Max. inlet flow: 0.25 m³/s
- Max. outlet flow: 0.3543 m³/s

Figure 14. Syrup tank

Three transfer chains are used in this virtual factory to transfer the cargo onto adjacent conveyors (see Figure.15). Each chain is composed of loading rollers and three chain tracks where:

- Chain rail travel: 0.04 m
- Maximum transport speed: 0.45 m/s
- Maximum chain speed: 0.45 m/s

Figure 16. Transfer chain.

The plant contains a heavy-duty motorized turntable, typically used for sorting pallets (see Figure.16). It is equipped with freely rotating peripheral rollers and pre-installed sensors. This table is characterized by:

- Roll radius: 0.045m
- Maximum transport speed: 0.45 m/s
- Table rotation speed: 0.7 rad/s
- Range of capacitive sensors: 0 - 0.1 m

Figure 16. Turning table.

The smart factory is based on emerging technologies that can transform all current production logic and business processes, leading to a profound change in organizations.

In our virtual factory, we used the following technologies with the same characteristics offered by the software Factory IO:

4.2 Wireless sensors

➤ *Capacitive sensor*

The capacitive sensor is a proximity or displacement sensor equipped with sensitive measurement electrodes and a capacitor, which allows the type of finished product to be recognized without contact.

An LED on this sensor indicates whether an item is within its detection range. Depending on the configuration used, either digital or analog output value can be obtained (See Figure.18).

- LED: green (detection)
- Detectable materials: solids and liquids.
- Detection range: 0 - 0.2m.

Figure 17. A proximity sensor is used for close detection of finished products.

➤ *Diffuse sensor*

Twenty-four photoelectric sensors are used in this factory. Their main role is the detection of the presence of the raw material and the movement of the finished products. They are characterized by:

- LED: red (detection)
- Detectable materials: solids
- Detection range: 0 - 1.6 m

➤ *Vision sensor*

- The vision sensor (refer to Figures. 18 and 19) can identify the colors of product bases, lids, and raw materials LED: red (detection).
- Detectable materials: raw materials, product bases, product covers.
- Detection range: 0.3 - 2 m.

Figure 18. Vision sensor.

This sensor can be customised to detect more than one part type by selecting the appropriate configuration:

- Any Numeric: Provides four numerical inputs indicating which object was detected. It returns a value that represents the discovered element.
- All ID: Returns a unique (random) value identifying the discovered object. It can be utilised similarly to barcode or RFID readers.

Figure 19. Loading of finished product to warehouses using a vision sensor.

4.3 RFID technology

Data from RFID tags can be read and written using this technology. In Factory IO software, a single-trigger communication architecture is employed, in which the controller sends a command to the reader and waits for a response. With the exception of raw components, lids, and product bases, nearly every item has an active tag. When RFID tags are in front of the reader, they are detected at a distance of 0.5 meters (see Figure. 20). Only one tag can be interrogate at a time by the RFID scanner.

Figure 20. RFID technology in the virtual factory

4.4 Cobotic

The machining center is a station for making covers and bases from raw materials. In the virtual factory, we used two collaborative robots (Cobots) in each station; a robot for the boxes manufacturing and the second for juice manufacturing.

During simulation, each product type takes a different time interval: 6 seconds for producing juice and 3 seconds for making a can. Once the operation is complete, the robot places the product on the output base (see Figure.21).

Figure 21. Collaborative production robot.

In general, the production operation (see Figure.22) can be reset, halted, or restarted as necessary. Through the electrical panel adjacent to the save door, you can communicate with the machining centre:

- Emergency: results in an emergency stop, which stops the CNC and the articulated robot. Only by turning off the emergency button and pressing the reset button can the station be reset following an emergency halt.
- Start: turns the station on
- Stop: stops both the articulated robot and the CNC. To restart, use the Start or Reset button.
- Reset : resets the station.

Two chimney lights placed above the protection provide information on the current status:

- Green light : not occupied.
- Yellow light : busy.
- Red LED: There is an error (incorrect element detected at the input bay).

Figure 22. Production phase using the production robot

4.5 Pick and Place Robot

Two pick and place robots are used in each station of the virtual factory. The first robot plays the role of the filling machine, while the second plays the role of the shrink-wrapping machine. To ensure a correct fit of the finished products, these latter must be aligned by the positioning bars (see Figure.23 and Figure.24).

- X-axis travel : 1
- Z axis stroke : 0.625 m
- Arm and pick-up speed: 2 m/s
- Z-axis rotation in 90° increments (arm and gripper).

Figure 23. Pick and place robot plays the role the filling machine

Figure 24. Pick and place robot plays the role of the shrink-wrapping machine.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The connected factory will be an environment where new technologies (such as cobotics, artificial intelligence, and the smart sensors) will allow a drastic increase in productivity. It is a new mode of production that uses digital technologies to produce goods and monitors its activity in real-time to optimize its operation.

A future factory is a new approach used for production resources management. Its goal is to create smart factories that are more flexible and efficient in terms of production and resource management. The intelligent factory paves the way for a new industrial revolution by using several innovative technologies that will have to master the entire life cycle management of the company's products or services.

Faced with the continuous and rapid evolution of the industrial environment, characterized by digitalization, all companies are obliged to meet the requirements of their customers in terms of costs, quality, and deadlines.

In this article, we have given a concise presentation of an example of an ordinary factory that is transformed into an intelligent factory using new technologies such as smart sensors. These latter can measure and identify events related to the machine condition (functional or not functional), they can bring transparency to and optimize material and process flows, etc. In sum, sensors can provide machines the ability to see, detect and communicate more intelligently. The design and simulation of the intelligent factory are applied using the software Factory IO. This latter allowed us to design and simulate a complete industrial system. It is equipped with a 360° view system, allowing to preview all the operations of the virtual factory without operator intervention and to optimize the production lines using various technologies.

As a perspective, we want to improve the virtual factory by integrating the Internet of Things solution and applying one of the techniques of artificial intelligence to manage and optimize the different manufacturing processes.

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